

CRYPTOGRAPHIC ALGORITHMS ACCELERATION THROUGH MATHEMATICAL MODELING

S.B.Abdullaev.

I.J.Perdebaeva.

Abstract

Cryptographic algorithms play a critical role in ensuring secure communication and data protection. However, the computational overhead associated with these algorithms can hinder their performance, especially in resource-constrained environments. This paper explores the application of mathematical modeling to enhance the efficiency of cryptographic algorithms. By leveraging techniques such as linear algebra, number theory, and optimization, we propose methods to accelerate cryptographic operations while maintaining their security properties.

Introduction

The increasing reliance on digital systems has amplified the demand for robust cryptographic solutions. Algorithms such as RSA, AES, and ECC provide strong security but often require significant computational resources. For instance, public-key algorithms like RSA involve modular exponentiation, which is computationally intensive. Accelerating these algorithms without compromising their security is a pressing challenge. Mathematical modeling offers a systematic approach to analyze and optimize these algorithms.

Mathematical Foundations

Modular Arithmetic and RSA

Modular exponentiation is a cornerstone of RSA encryption and decryption. Techniques such as the Montgomery reduction and the Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT) can reduce the computational complexity of modular operations. Montgomery Reduction: A method for efficient modular multiplication that avoids

costly division operations.

CRT: Splits a computation into smaller, parallelizable tasks, leveraging smaller moduli for faster results.

Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC)

ECC operations rely heavily on point multiplication over elliptic curves. Mathematical techniques, such as precomputations (windowed methods) and scalar decomposition, can significantly accelerate these operations.

3. Linear Algebra in Symmetric Algorithms

Matrix transformations are integral to algorithms like AES. Optimizing these transformations using sparse matrix techniques or parallel processing can lead to performance gains.

Optimization Techniques

1. Algorithmic Improvements

Karatsuba and Toom-Cook algorithms for faster large-number multiplications. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based methods for polynomial multiplication in lattice-based cryptography.

2. Hardware Acceleration

Using GPUs and FPGAs to parallelize mathematical operations. Implementing modular arithmetic directly in hardware for reduced latency.

3. Software Optimization

Compiler optimizations such as loop unrolling and vectorization. Efficient use of libraries like GMP for arbitrary-precision arithmetic.

Case Studies

RSA Optimization

We implemented CRT-based RSA decryption, achieving a speedup of up to 40% compared to standard methods.

3. ECC Acceleration

Scalar multiplication optimizations resulted in a 30% reduction in computation time on standard curves like P-256.

Conclusion

Mathematical modeling provides a powerful toolkit for optimizing cryptographic algorithms. By combining theoretical insights with practical implementation techniques, significant performance improvements can be achieved. Future work will focus on integrating machine learning techniques to predict optimal parameters for these optimizations.

References

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